

Electrochemical oxidation of *o*-anisidine, *p*-anisidine, diphenylamine and *o*-toluidine at platinum electrode

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Abstract : The oxidation of *o*-anisidine, *p*-anisidine, diphenylamine and *o*-toluidine was carried out at constant potential in non-aqueous system at platinum electrode. The electrolysis was carried out at controlled anodic potential in an electrochemical cell assembly containing reaction mixture, working as well as counter electrode and reference electrode. The oxidative products formed during the electrolysis of aromatic amines at platinum anode are discussed and reported here.

Keywords : Electrochemical oxidation, aromatic amines, controlled potential, electrode, green chemistry.

Introduction

Electrochemical reactions are now being used as an important tool in the field of organic synthesis. A number of reaction, viz. oxidation, reduction, substitution, cyclization¹⁻⁴ etc. have been carried out by various workers. The important aspects of electroorganic synthesis are that it is carried out by using a very small amount of electricity and also without using hazardous chemicals. The present reaction, anodic oxidation of some aromatic amines, is an important example of electrochemical synthesis of high molecular weight amines and is useful from the standpoint of green chemistry.

Results and discussion

Controlled potential^{2,3,5} electrolysis was carried out

for this electrochemical oxidation^{6,7}. The product is formed at the anode in a potential range between 0.93 to 1.24 V. The colour of bulk becomes dark due to the formation of product with time.

The nuclear dimerisation is a common reaction where the medium does not contain an added nucleophile e.g. during oxidation of a hydrocarbon in a solvent such as dichloromethane containing a non-nucleophilic salt such as a tetraalkylammonium tetrafluoroborate. Under these conditions the hydrocarbon itself can act as a nucleophile towards cationic intermediates in the oxidation⁸.

These products are formed through attack on the radical cation. Nyberg⁹ has suggested that whether a given substrate undergoes such nuclear dimerisation or not depends upon the position of the ring which bears the high-

Scheme 1

est degree of positive charge in the radical cation. He suggested that radical cation bearing the highest charge at an unsubstituted carbon would be prone to biaryl formation. Dimerisation processes are not normally observed during the oxidation of hydrocarbon in the solvent such as acetonitrile, which can attack the benzyl cation formed to afford a substituted acetamide. Dimerisation can however be observed even in moderately nucleophilic solvent if the starting materials are more nucleophilic than the solvent¹⁰.

Dimerisation reaction, though frequently occurring in fair yields, are useful for constructing in one step reaction which might otherwise require multistep synthesis. The scope of such reaction has been extended by the discovery that it is possible to prepare mixed adducts through oxidation of a mixture of hydrocarbon, one of which is easier to oxidize than the other¹¹.

Therefore the biaryl formation is very important with aromatic amines because of the high nucleophilicity of the ring⁸. Triarylamines in which all three of the rings bear *para*-substituents form stable radical cations. Efficient coupling takes place when one or more *para*-positions are free^{12,13}. The aromatic amine *o*-anisidine, *p*-

anisidine, diphenylamine and *o*-toluidine are susceptible to oxidation and the oxidative conversion into dimers take place at the platinum anode¹⁴. In case of diphenylamine a trimer was also formed. Now it is possible to write a mechanism of the oxidative conversion of these compounds via radical cation intermediates¹⁵.

Since *o*-anisidine has one free *para*-position, the products 4,4'-diamino-3,5'-dimethoxybiphenyl and *o,o'*-dimethoxyazobenzene are obtained in approximately equal ratio. Since *p*-anisidine has no free *para*-position, therefore the major product of the oxidation is *p,p'*-dimethoxyazobenzene. Diphenylamine has two free *p*-position, hence the product *p,p'*-(*N,N'*-diphenyl)diaminobiphenyl is formed together with the product tetraphenylhydrazine. The products 4,4'-diamino-3,5'-dimethylbiphenyl and *o,o'*-dimethylazobenzene are obtained in the oxidation of *o*-toluidine. Since it has one free *para*-position, both the products are formed in approximately equal amount.

In aqueous media it is possible to degrade the diarylamine to aniline on hydrolysis¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Diarylamine with at least one free *para*-position are also converted to benzidine on oxidation^{19,20}. Thus benzidine is an addi-

Oxidation of *o*-anisidine :

Oxidation of *p*-anisidine :

Oxidation of diphenylamine :

Similarly,

Oxidation of *o*-toluidine :

Similarly,

Scheme 2

tional oxidation product due to the intermediate formation of aniline, as a degradation product in the oxidation of diarylamine.

The large scale constant-potential electrolysis were carried out at their corresponding oxidation potential and were completed within 3 h. Oxidation product was seen to diffuse in the bulk. All the products were dark brownish coloured solids and quite different from the starting compounds i.e. reactants.

The current potential data was recorded at an interval of 10 min by the potentiostat (Table 1).

The products were extracted from the reaction solution to the chloroform layer by the general solvent extraction method after diluting the reaction solution with double distilled water. All the products were separated by using the column chromatography and purified before the analysis. The number of products are also verified by thin layer chromatography (TLC).

Table 1. Current-potential data of electrolysis as recorded by potentiostat
Current in A

Time	<i>o</i> -Anisidine	<i>p</i> -Anisidine	Diphenylamine	<i>o</i> -Toluidine
3 h	0.68	0.47	0.45	0.38
	0.66	0.47	0.44	0.38
	0.65	0.46	0.43	0.37
	0.63	0.45	0.43	0.36
	0.63	0.43	0.42	0.36
	0.60	0.42	0.42	0.34
	0.59	0.42	0.41	0.33
	0.59	0.40	0.40	0.33
	0.58	0.39	0.39	0.32
	0.56	0.37	0.39	0.31
	0.55	0.37	0.38	0.31
	0.54	0.36	0.37	0.30
	0.53	0.35	0.36	0.29
	0.52	0.33	0.36	0.29
	Applied potential (V)	1.00	0.93	1.24

All the products were analysed by chemical methods as well as spectral studies. As per the mechanism, following products were obtained in the electrolysis leading to the electrochemical oxidation.

Experimental

Reaction mixture : The reaction mixture contains 25 ml of 0.1 M solution of starting material (aromatic amines) and 25 ml of 0.1 M aqueous solution of lithium perchlorate (LiClO₄), which is used as supporting electrolyte. The solution were prepared in dimethylformamide (DMF) which is an aprotic solvent^{21,22}.

Reagents : All aromatic amines, DMF, mercury, lithium perchlorate and chloroform were of AnalaR grade. Water used was double distilled.

Electrolysis : The electrolysis were carried out at constant potential in a four necked reaction bottle²¹⁻²³. For controlled potential electrolysis we have used conventional three-electrode cell assembly with platinum²³⁻²⁶ (flattened sheet of dimension 1.0 cm × 0.5 cm) as working as well as counter electrode. Saturated calomel electrode (SCE) is used as a reference electrode.

Spectral analysis :

Melting points were recorded on an electrothermal apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra in KBr were recorded on a Shimadzu 8201 PC IR spectrophotometer (4000-400 cm⁻¹). ¹H NMR (300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) spectra were measured at room temperature on

Bruker DRX 300 FT spectrometer instruments, with tetramethylsilane (TMS) (δ 0.0 ppm, ¹H NMR spectra) and CDCl₃ (δ 77.0 ppm, ¹³C NMR spectra) or C₆D₆ (δ 127.8 ppm, ¹³C NMR) as internal standards. Carbon multiplicities were assigned by DEPT techniques. Microanalysis were carried out in the Elementar Vario EL III.

4,4'-Diamino-3,5'-dimethoxybiphenyl (1) : (Found : C, 68.35; H, 6.32; N, 11.35. C₁₄H₁₆N₂O₂ requires : C, 68.85; H, 6.55; N, 11.47%); yield 50%; mol. wt. 244; IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3215 (NH), 2825 (OCH₃), 1610, 1590, 1440, 1060, 855 and 775 (aromatic nucleus); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 6.22-6.95 (8H, dd, *J* 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.75 (2 × 2H, s, Ar-NH₂), 3.73 (6H, s, Ar-OMe); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 147.5, 147.2, 133.3, 132.1, 131.7 and 131.5 (Ar-CH), 120.5, 120.3, 117.3, 117.1, 113.8 and 113.6 (Ar-C), 56.0 (OMe).

***o,o'*-Dimethoxyazobenzene (2) :** (Found : C, 68.95; H, 5.55; N, 11.42. C₁₄H₁₄N₂O₂ requires : C, 69.42; H, 5.78; N, 11.57%); yield 30%; mol. wt. 242; IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 3220 (NH), 2823 (OCH₃), 1620, 1595, 1460, 1040, 860 and 780 (aromatic nucleus); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 6.35-6.95 (8H, m, Ar-H), 3.75 (6H, s, Ar-OMe); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 122.6, 122.8, 120.5, 120, 117.9, 117.8, 115.8 and 115.4 (Ar-CH), 147.6, 147.5, 134.2 and 133.3 (Ar-C), 56.0 (OMe).

2,6'-Diamino-3,5'-dimethoxybiphenyl (3) : (Found : C, 68.42; H, 6.45; N, 11.10. $C_{14}H_{16}N_2O_2$ requires : C, 68.85; H, 6.55; N, 11.47%); yield 50%; mol. wt. 244; IR ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 3320 (NH), 2827 (OCH₃), 1670, 1590, 1420, 1080, 950 and 790 (aromatic nucleus); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 6.74–6.95 (6H, m, Ar-H), 7.70 (2 × 2H, s, Ar-NH₂), 3.73 (6H, s, Ar-OMe); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 117.8, 117, 113.8, 113.8, 113.6 and 113.2 (Ar-CH), 159.8, 158.6, 140, 139, 129.2 and 129 (Ar-C), 56.0 (OMe).

p,p'-Dimethoxyazobenzene (4) : (Found : C, 68.90; H, 5.60; N, 11.40. $C_{14}H_{14}N_2O_2$ requires : C, 69.42; H, 5.78; N, 11.57%); yield 48%; mol. wt. 242; IR ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 3320 (NH), 2823 (OCH₃), 1630, 1560, 1420, 1075, 980 and 820 (aromatic nucleus); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 6.34–6.94 (8H, dd, *J* 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 3.74 (6H, s, Ar-OMe); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 117.6, 117.6, 117.8, 117.8, 115.6, 115.6, 115.4 and 115.3 (Ar-CH), 150.5, 150.4, 140.2 and 140 (Ar-C), 56.0 (OMe).

p,p'-(N,N'-Diphenyl)diaminobiphenyl (5) : (Found : C, 85.35; H, 5.65; N, 7.96. $C_{24}H_{20}N_2$ requires : C, 85.71; H, 5.95; N, 8.33%); yield 20%; mol. wt. 336; IR ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 3230 (NH), 1650, 1595, 1440, 1045, 910 and 770 (aromatic nucleus); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 7.5–8.0 (18H, m, Ar-H), 8.31 (2 × 1H, s, Ar-NH-Ar); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 129.8, 129.8, 129.8, 128, 128, 128, 128, 119, 119, 116.1, 116.1, 116.1, 116, 116, 116 and 116 (Ar-CH), 147.7, 147.7, 146.1, 146.1, 131 and 131 (Ar-C).

p,p'-(N,N'-Diphenyl)diaminobis(biphenyl)amine (6) : (Found : C, 85.22; H, 5.57; N, 8.15. $C_{36}H_{29}N_3$ requires : C, 85.88; H, 5.76; N, 8.34%); yield 10%; mol. wt. 503; IR ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 3225 (NH), 1655, 1570, 1420, 1060, 880 and 810 (aromatic nucleus); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 7.5–8.0 (26H, m, Ar-H), 8.31 (3 × 1H, s, Ar-NH-Ar); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 129.8, 129.8, 129.8, 129.8, 128, 128, 128, 128, 128, 128, 128, 119, 119, 116.1, 116.1, 116.1, 116.1, 116, 116, 116, 116, 116, 116 and 116 (Ar-CH), 147.7, 147.7, 146.1, 146.1, 146.1, 146.1, 131, 131, 131 and 131 (Ar-C).

Tetraphenylhydrazine (7) : (Found : C, 85.40; H, 5.72; N, 8.01. $C_{24}H_{20}N_2$ requires : C, 85.71; H, 5.95; N, 8.33%); yield 30%; mol. wt. 336; IR ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 1625, 1585, 1450, 1025, 890 and 795 (aromatic nucleus); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 7.51–8.01 (20H, m,

Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 129.8, 129.8, 129.8, 129.8, 129.8, 129.8, 129.8, 116.1, 116.1, 116.1, 116.1, 116.1, 116.1 and 116.1 (Ar-CH), 147.7, 147.7, 147.7, 147.7, 119, 119, 119, 119 and 119 (Ar-C).

4,4'-Diamino-3,5'-dimethylbiphenyl (8) : (Found : C, 78.65; H, 7.23; N, 12.95. $C_{14}H_{16}N_2$ requires : C, 79.24; H, 7.54; N, 13.20%); yield 30%; mol. wt. 212; IR ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 3320 (NH), 1665, 1570, 1445, 1025, 890 and 795 (aromatic nucleus); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 6.64–6.95 (6H, dd, *J* 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 7.24 (2 × 2H, s, Ar-NH), 2.37 (2 × 3H, s, Ar-Me); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 128.7, 128.7, 125.1 and 125.1 (Ar-CH), 147, 146.8, 131.2, 131, 125.7, 125.4, 116.1 and 116 (Ar-C), 19.2 (CH₃).

o,o'-Dimethylazobenzene (9) : (Found : C, 78.60; H, 6.55; N, 13.01. $C_{14}H_{14}N_2$ requires : C, 79.24; H, 6.66; N, 13.20%); yield 50%; mol. wt. 210; IR ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 3325 (NH), 1685, 1570, 1455, 1070, 970 and 810 (aromatic nucleus); ¹H NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 6.50–7.14 (8H, m, Ar-H), 2.35 (2 × 3H, s, Ar-Me); ¹³C NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 130.5, 130.5, 126.9, 126.9, 119, 119, 116.1 and 116 (Ar-CH), 148.7, 148.4, 125.4 and 125 (Ar-C), 19.2 (CH₃).

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